

GENERAL PREVENTION OF OFFENSES CARRIED OUT BY THE OFFENSE PREVENTION SERVICES OF INTERNAL AFFAIRS BODIES

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Abstract

The article discusses the activities of general prevention of offenses carried out by the offense prevention services of internal affairs bodies, and offers proposals and recommendations for the more effective organization of this activity.

Key words: internal affairs bodies, offense prevention services, offenses, general prevention of offenses, measures.

In the implementation of offense prevention activities in the social life of our country, the offense prevention services of internal affairs bodies play an important role. In particular, the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On the Prevention of Offenses"[1] outlines the system of bodies and institutions that carry out and participate in offense prevention, their powers, and one of the bodies carrying out this activity is the internal affairs bodies of the Republic of Uzbekistan. In the system of internal affairs bodies, the main structural unit broadly implementing offense prevention is the Offense Prevention Service of the Public Safety Department of the Ministry of Internal Affairs, which in turn coordinates the activities of offense prevention units of internal affairs bodies.

Typically, the offense prevention services of the internal affairs bodies carry out their offense prevention activities primarily in the form of general prevention of offenses in accordance with the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On the Prevention of Offenses"[2]. General prevention of offenses is the activity of bodies and institutions that carry out and participate in offense prevention to prevent offenses, identify and eliminate the causes of offenses and the conditions that contribute to them.

If we pay attention to the definitions given by the scientific community to general crime prevention, for example, N.B. Kurbanov notes that general crime prevention refers to the development of economic, political, social, and other institutions to combat crime, the creation of conditions for the spiritual and educational development of people, the identification of various causes of crime, and the prevention of the harmful influence of the conditions that cause crime.

M.Yu. Kerzhner and G.T. Abdullahodjaev defined general prevention as "organized at the state level and is an important direction of state policy in organizing the fight against crime." [4] Other sources state that general crime prevention refers to the activities of crime prevention entities to prevent, identify, and eliminate the causes of their occurrence, as well as the conditions that contribute to their occurrence.

It can be said that these opinions do not reflect all aspects of general crime prevention, that is, we can witness that the given definitions do not reveal all the specific features, goals, and objectives of this type of prevention.

K.R. Abdurasulova believes that "general social prevention encompasses socio-political, organizational, legal, and educational measures aimed at identifying the causes and conditions of offenses, eliminating or neutralizing them, combating other antisocial acts, educating citizens and officials in the spirit of respect for the law, and re-educating those who violate the rules of social morality." The reason is that the purpose of general crime prevention is to explain the role and significance of antisocial behavior against a group of individuals or the general public at the same time, as well as the legal consequences arising from the commission of the offense, the causes of the offense and the conditions that made it possible, the methods and forms of committing the offense, the role and significance of victimological factors, to promote the content and essence of the adopted laws and to call for awareness.

At the same time, the ability to simultaneously exert a preventive influence on several subjects of social relations and the availability of time savings, low expenditure of energy and resources, and a comprehensive approach to crime prevention can be noted as features and advantages of general crime prevention, implemented by crime prevention services.

According to the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On the Prevention of Offenses," measures for general crime prevention are:

- development and implementation of state and other programs for the prevention of offenses;
- conducting legal propaganda among the population;
- identification and elimination of the causes of the commission of offenses and the conditions conducive to them, as well as the submission of submissions on the elimination of the causes of the commission of offenses and the conditions conducive to them.

General crime prevention may also include other measures in accordance with the law.

It should be noted that, as a rule, the effectiveness and success of each implemented measure is directly related to the clear and perfect definition of the grounds and procedure for its implementation, it is advisable that general crime prevention measures have the same basis and procedure.

It can be said that in the development and implementation of state programs and other programs for the prevention of offenses in our country, the crime prevention services of the internal affairs bodies participate directly, and after the approval of the developed programs by the relevant leadership, in the implementation of these programs, that is, in the execution of these programs, they interact with other sectoral services of the internal affairs bodies, state bodies and organizations directly engaged in crime prevention, other bodies and institutions participating in it, as well as civil society institutions.

Furthermore, when developing these programs, it is advisable for the crime prevention services of internal affairs bodies to focus on high-probability offenses in the programs developed for the coming years. This should be based on the results of accurate reporting and analysis of offenses from previous years and take into account the criminogenic situation in the regions. In this regard, it is advisable to pay special attention to the wide coverage of cooperation issues with state bodies and civil society institutions that directly carry out and participate in crime prevention. The reason is that current analysis shows an increase in cases of fraud using information and communication technologies and bicycle thefts in Tashkent city (in November 2024, 76 criminal cases were initiated for bicycle thefts). Based on this, we

believe it is necessary to consider these general crime prevention measures in the programs developed for the upcoming period.

Another measure of general crime prevention is legal education among the population. Indeed, legal education plays an important role in crime prevention. The purpose of legal education is to convey the content and essence of issues related to the legal rights and obligations of members of society, particularly the general public, and thereby raise the legal awareness and culture of citizens. After all, raising the legal awareness and culture of the population is one of the important directions for developing civil society. In other words, by raising legal awareness and legal culture in society and strengthening legality, the legal literacy of the population will increase, their legal awareness and culture will improve, and their respect for the law will grow, leading to a reduction in offenses in the future. This will yield positive results in the future activities of the crime prevention services of internal affairs bodies.

Particularly in raising the legal awareness and culture of the population, it is important for law enforcement agencies to organize legal activities in cooperation with civil society institutions, widely utilizing their capabilities - in other words, to strengthen legislative education.

As the First President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, Islam Karimov, noted, fostering respect and obedience to the Constitution and laws depends greatly on employees working in state bodies, particularly internal affairs bodies. Further improving the foundations of the rule of law in our country and raising the legal awareness and culture of the population is also a crucial task for us.

In our country, since the early days of independence, serious attention has been paid to improving the legal literacy of the population and raising their legal awareness and culture. Specifically, to increase the legal culture and social activity of the population and improve the legal education of citizens, the Oliy Majlis of the Republic of Uzbekistan adopted a resolution "On the National Program for Raising Legal Culture in Society."

The President of the Republic of Uzbekistan also issued a Decree "On the Fundamental Improvement of the System for Raising Legal Awareness and Legal Culture in Society." This Decree approved the "Concept of Raising Legal Culture in Society." These normative legal acts are particularly important for the crime prevention services of internal affairs bodies in performing tasks related to raising the legal awareness and culture of the population.

It can be said that legal culture, along with legislation and ensuring legal guarantees for citizens, is a policy of state importance. This situation is one of the criminogenic factors affecting the state of offenses in society's social life. Statistical data shows that in the republic, during the first 10 months of 2024, a total of 27,765 promotional activities were carried out in the mass media: 5,410 on television, 2,423 on radio, 19,018 on the Internet, 913 in newspapers and magazines, and 8,802 videos. Additionally, 639,355 promotional materials on crime prevention were prepared: 614,471 booklets and 24,885 banners. These efforts serve to raise the legal awareness and culture of the population in local areas.

It can be said that if the subject conducting legal propaganda does not approach this task responsibly, the participants will be indifferent to him and his words. As a result, the legal propaganda carried out will be carried out only for reporting, in other words, "superficially," "to show." Specifically, the First President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, Islam Karimov, noted that "the rapid development of society on the path of democracy and the

success of reforms being implemented in this direction largely depend on the level of legal awareness and legal culture of people." A high legal culture is the foundation of a democratic society and an indicator of the maturity of the legal system.

Another measure of general crime prevention is the identification and elimination of the causes of crime and the conditions contributing to it, as well as the submission of submissions on the elimination of the causes of crime and the conditions contributing to it. Crime prevention services of internal affairs bodies are also authorized to submit submissions to state bodies and civil society institutions, the purpose of which is to prevent similar cases in the future.

Over the 10 months of 2024, law enforcement agencies submitted a total of 80,168 submissions to eliminate the causes of violations.

The fact that the crime prevention services of the internal affairs bodies, within their powers, regularly submit proposals to enterprises, institutions and organizations, as well as civil society institutions to identify and eliminate the causes and conditions contributing to the commission of crimes in the regions, as well as the organization of thorough discussions among the general public on each case, will significantly contribute to the prevention of crimes in the future.

In conclusion, it can be said that the activities of the crime prevention services of the internal affairs bodies in the field of general crime prevention are characterized by a wide range and unique multifaceted nature. In particular, the main purpose of their activities is to raise the legal awareness and culture of citizens in our country, prevent the commission of offenses by understanding the inevitability of liability for offenses, inform the general public about the offence and the social danger of the persons who committed it, methods and means of committing offenses, achieve self-defense, as well as social adaptation and social rehabilitation of persons who have suffered from offenses, along with moral correction of persons with antisocial behavior, prone to committing offenses and persons who have committed offenses,

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